

BACTERIOLOGICAL ANALYSIS OF CASES DIAGNOSED AS ENTERIC FEVER IN SOKOTO – NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

The study was conducted to determine the proportion of confirmed enteric or typhoid cases as well as non-typhoid salmonellosis among patients clinically diagnosed or suspected to have typhoid or enteric fever. Serum and fecal samples were collected from two hundred (200) patients presenting with enteric fever in Sokoto metropolis to determine the prevalence of non-typhoid salmonella and the reliability of the Widal test. The serum samples were tested for Widal reaction using Antec Widal Diagnostic Kit, while the fecal samples from the same patients were subjected to cultural isolation and identification of salmonellae. The results showed that 132(66%) of the patients were positive for Widal test. Salmonellae were isolated from 11 (5.5%) comprising 5(3.8%) and 6(8.8%) from Widal positive and Widal negative samples respectively. Two of the isolates were non-typhoidal *Salmonella*, one each from Widal positive and Widal negative patients. Typhoid *Salmonella* were recovered from 9(4.5%) of the patients, of which 4(44.4%) and 5(55.6%) were from Widal positive and Widal negative patients respectively. Other organisms isolated and identified were *Shigella* spp., Protozoan cysts and helminth ova.

KEYWORDS: Enteric fever, Widal test; Salmonella, non-typhoid.

INTRODUCTION

Enteric or typhoid fever is endemic and sometimes occurs in epidemic proportions in many tropical countries including Nigeria (Olubuyide, 1992). The clinical presentation of typhoid fever, usually as pyrexia of unknown origin is often misleading in a region where malaria is endemic, accounting for about 75% of cases of fever (Grange, 1994). This has led to under-diagnosis of typhoid fever in many instances. On the other hand, the practice of making a diagnosis of typhoid fever on the laboratory value of Widal test, regardless of standard quality control measures, is now quite rampant and responsible for the current rate of over diagnosis of the disease (Cook, 1985). The antigens that stimulate the antibodies, which are detected by Widal test, are shared by a very large number of organisms that make up the salmonella genus as well as by some other related organisms (Guerrant, 1986).

Definite diagnosis of typhoid fever is based on cultures of blood, bone marrow and stool (Homik, 1985; Edelman and Levine, 1986). In Nigeria, because of the technical difficulties, and cost involved in cultural isolation and identification of the causative organisms, there is over reliance on the Widal test. The implication therefore is that if a patient has a “significant typhoidal antibody titre”, treatment of typhoid fever is often commenced even without a consideration of the clinical signs and symptoms. Patients with abdominal catastrophes other than typhoid fever but with a “significant Widal test” are labeled as cases of typhoid fever (Osime and Eghafona, 2003) and are so treated. Many of such patients wrongly diagnosed and so treated run the risk of having life threatening complications resulting from various pathological intra-abdominal conditions.

The present study was conducted to determine the relative proportion of confirmed enteric or typhoid cases as well as non-typhoid salmonellosis among patients clinically diagnosed or suspected as typhoid or enteric fever in Sokoto, Nigeria.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Microbiological Examination of Stool Samples

A total of 200 stool samples from patients presenting as enteric fever cases, were examined over a period of 4 months (February 2004 to May 2004).

Stool samples obtained from patients were examined for salmonellae; by enrichment in selenite F broth, plating on desoxycholate citrate and brilliant green selective agar, testing for Urease, oxidase and indole production, and reaction in triple sugar iron agar, lactose, sucrose, manitol, Dulcitol and lysine (Oboegbulem, 1993; Cowan and Steel, 1993).

Serotyping of the *Salmonella* isolates was based on Kaufmanns-white scheme (Rowe and Hall, 1980) using commercial O, H and Vi, antisera from central Research Institute, Kasauli, India. The fecal samples were also examined for protozoan cysts helminth ova, and hookworm's larvae.

Widal Agglutination test

Serological diagnosis of enteric fever was carried out by the Widal agglutination technique described by Gilles and Dodd, (1976) and using commercial Widal test kit obtained from Antec Diagnostic products, UK. Each serum sample was reacted against the suspension of standard O and H typhoid and paratyphoid antigens. Agglutination at a titre of 1:80 and above for typhoid or paratyphoid was taken as indicative of enteric fever in this study.

RESULTS

Incidence of enteric fever (typhoid and paratyphoid)

Enteric fever bacilli (*S. typhi* and *S. paratyphi*) were recovered in 9(4.5%) out of 200 patients examined. Of the 200 patients investigated 132 (66%) gave a significant, titre of 1:80 and above for *S. typhi* and *S. paratyphi*. Positive agglutination lower than 1:80 was not considered significant. The number of patients showing both significant titres of Widal test and positive stool cultures for enteric bacilli was 4. The typhoid bacilli were not isolated from stool samples of 128 seropositive patients, but were recovered from 5 seronegative patients. One of the 132 serologically positive patients indicated paratyphoid infection due to *S. paratyphi* C, and the 68 seronegative patients also indicated paratyphoid infection with 1 due to *S. paratyphi* C.

Non-typhoid Salmonella Infection

Non-typhoid Salmonellae were recovered from two (2) patients; one of the patients was seropositive while the other was seronegative. The isolates were *S. typhimurium* and *S. enteritidis*. The non-typhoid salmonella accounted for 18.2% of the total salmonella isolates.

Infection due to other organisms

Shigella spp. was isolated from 5(2.5%) of the patients investigated. Four of the isolates were recovered from Widal positive patients and only one was from the Widal negative patients. Protozoan cysts, helminth ova were detected in 21(10.5%) of the patients investigated. Seventeen (8.5%) of these were recovered from patients positive to Widal test and the remaining 4(2%) were from those patients that are negative to Widal test.

DISCUSSION

Typhoid (enteric) fever infection appears to continue to be of a great public health hazard in developing countries. Poor sanitation and unhygienic environment aids in the spread of the infection. Definitive diagnoses of this illness in certain part of the world continue to be a major problem. The definitive

diagnosis, which is based on the isolation of the causative agent, is hampered by the economic hardship in the developing countries (Lateef, *et. al.*, 1996). Most cases of suspected typhoid fever have erroneously been confirmed based on a single serology (Widal test), frequently with the titres much lower than 1:80 in the study area.

Based on the positive stool cultures for *S. typhi* or *S. paratyphi*, only 9 (4.5%) of the patients were shown to be confirmed cases of typhoid, out of which, 5(2.5%) were from the seronegative group. Many of the cases of typhoid may in actual fact be due to non-typhoid salmonellae or other gastro-intestinal infections as revealed in our study.

The Widal test is affected by several factors that can lead to false negative and false positive results. Our findings showed that 5 of the positive isolate for typhoid bacilli were from the seronegative patient and only 4 positive isolates were from seropositive patients. This can be associated with factors such as previous exposure to salmonella infection (Olubuyide, 1992); self medication with antibiotic before presentation (Agbonlahor, *et. al.*, 1997); recipients of typhoid vaccine (Gupta, *et. al.*, 1985); presence of fimbrial antigens in the test suspension (Osime and Eghafona, 2003); possibility of cross-reaction of malaria sera to *S. typhi* antigen (Lateef, *et. al.*, 1996) and patients that are carrier (Agbonlahor, *et. al.*; 1997).

Greater proportions of the isolates were *S. typhi* and less than 20% of the isolates were *Salmonella paratyphi C*. This suggests that greater proportion of the population were exposed to *Salmonella typhi* than *S. paratyphi*. This is in line with the findings of Mohammed, *et. al.*, 1992; Olubuyide, 1992 and Osime and Eghafona, 2003, who reported that Nigeria is endemic for typhoid and that paratyphoid are less commonly encountered. *S. paratyphi* is the prevalent paratyphoid bacilli in the area as revealed by our study. The two serotypes of non-typhoid salmonella recovered in the study, namely *S. enteritidis* and *S. typhimurium* are among the principal causes of food borne salmonellosis. Their isolation in this region is of epidemiological significance.

CONCLUSION

Patients presenting, as enteric fever cases should therefore be thoroughly examined and samples collected for bacteriology and serology, to avoid assumed diagnosis of typhoid fever.

REFERENCES

- Alaribe, A.A.A.; Ejezie, G.C. and Ezedinachi E.N.U (1998). The prevalence of Salmonella among malaria patients in Calabar. *J. Med. Lab. Sci.*, 7:34-41
- Agbonlahor, D.E.; Aghahowa, M.O.; Idukpaye, O.; Agbonlahor, F.E.; *et. al.*, (1997). Baseline typhoidal antibody levels in apparently healthy Nigerians. *Nig. Qt. J. Hosp. Med.* 7(3): 242-245
- Cook, G.C.C (1985). Management of Typhoid fever. *Trop. Doc.* 15: 154 -159
- Cowan, S.T and Steel, K.J. (1993). Manual for the identification of Medical bacteria, 3rd (Edn.). Edited by G.I. Barrow and R.K.A. Fethar. Cambridge, University Press.
- Edelman, R.A. and Levine, M.M. (1986). Summary of International Workshop on typhoid fever. *Rev. Inf. Dis* 8: 329 – 249.
- Gilles, R.R. and Dodds, T.C (1976): the enteric fever, In: Bacteriology Illustrated, 4th edn. Churchill Livingstone, Edinburgh.
- Grange, A.O. (1994). A review of Typhoid fever in Africa. *The Postgrad. Med. J.* 1(2): 34 – 37

Guerrant, R.L. (1986). Salmonella infections. In Harrison's principles of Internal Medicine, 11th edn. McGraw Hill, New York, pp. 592 – 599

Gupta, S.P., Gupta, M.S., Bhardwaj, S. and Chugh, T.D. (1985): Current Clinical Patterns of Typhoid Fever- A prospective study. *J. Trop. Med. Hyg.* 88: 177-81.

Homik, R.B. (1985). Selective PHC strategies for control of disease in developing World: *Rev. Inf. Dis.* 1:535 – 546

Lateef, O., Femi, O. Ronke, O. Gbonyega, A., Mojo, A and Sola, A. (1996). Widal agglutination in Malaria infection. *Med. Rev.* 3 (6): 5-6

Mohammed, I.; Chikwem, J.O. and Gashau, W. (1992). Determination of Widal agglutination of the baseline titre for the diagnosis of typhoid fever in two Nigerian states. *Scand. J. Immunol.* 36 (11): 153 – 156.

Oboegbulem, S.I. (1993). Comparison of two enrichment and three selective media for isolation of salmonellae from chicken carcass rinse fluids and sewer swabs. *Int. J. Food Microbiol.* 18: 167 – 170

Olubuyide, I.O. (1992). Typhoid fever in the tropics. *Postgrad.Doc.Afr.* 14: 37 –41

Osime, C.O. and Eghafona, N (2003). Typhoid Antibodies in a Healthy population: Diagnostic significance in Nigeria. *The Nig. J. Sc. Res.* 4(1): 54 – 60

Rowe, B. and Hall, M.L. (1980). Kaufman-white scheme Division of Enteric pathogens. Public Health Laboratory, London.

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